

Protocol for Immunohistochemical Labelling and Stereological Analysis of Dopaminergic Neurons in the Mouse Substantia Nigra

Nicolas Giguère^{1,2}, Claudie Beaulieu^{1,2}, Amandine Even^{1,2}, Alex Tchung^{1,2}, Soraya Paquereau--Gaboreau^{1,2}, Rabia R Khawaja^{3,4}, Julie Andersen⁵, Kay L. Double⁶, Ana Maria Cuervo^{3,4}, Darren Moore⁷, and Louis-Eric Trudeau^{1,2}

1. Department of Pharmacology and Physiology, Department of Neurosciences, Faculty of Medicine, Université de Montréal, Montréal, Quebec, Canada
2. Neural Signalling and Circuitry Research Group (SNC), Center for Interdisciplinary Research on the Brain and Learning (CIRCA), Université de Montréal, Montréal, Quebec, Canada
3. Institute for Aging Studies, Albert Einstein College of Medicine, Bronx, NY, USA
4. Department of Developmental and Molecular Biology, Albert Einstein College of Medicine, Bronx, NY, USA.
5. Buck Institute for Research on Aging, Novato, CA, USA.
6. Brain and Mind Centre and School of Medical Sciences (Neuroscience), Faculty of Medicine and Health, The University of Sydney, Sydney, Australia.
7. Department of Neurodegenerative Science, Van Andel Institute, Grand Rapids, Michigan, USA

Correspondence should be addressed to:

Louis-Eric Trudeau, Ph.D.

Professor

Department of pharmacology and physiology

Department of neurosciences

Faculty of Medicine

Université de Montréal

Phone: 514-343-5692

Email: louis-eric.trudeau@umontreal.ca

Abstract

This protocol provides a detailed guide for the harvesting, fixation, sectioning, and immunohistochemical staining of dopaminergic (DA) neurons in sections of the substantia nigra of mouse brains, focusing on tyrosine hydroxylase (TH) staining and the counting of the number of DA neurons using unbiased stereological counting methods. The protocol was assembled by members of the PD-AGE network composed of leading experts in the fields of ageing and Parkinson's disease and aims to standardise across laboratories an otherwise commonly used method to ensure reproducibility and reliability in immunohistochemical staining for TH and stereological analyses. This document is intended for researchers involved in comparative studies of mouse models of Parkinson's disease and ageing, with a particular emphasis on assessing dopaminergic neuron integrity in the substantia nigra.

Introduction

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder including multiple motor and non-motor symptoms. The progressive appearance of the characteristic motor symptoms has been linked to the progressive degeneration of dopaminergic (DA) neurons in the substantia nigra pars compacta (SNpc), a population of neurons that is distinctly vulnerable to a range of cellular stressors linked to mitochondrial, lysosomal or oxidative perturbations (Giguère et al., 2019). With advancing age being the most significant risk factor for PD, understanding the interplay between ageing and disease pathology is critical for identifying therapeutic targets (Rocha et al., 2023). Ageing-associated cellular changes, including mitochondrial and lysosomal dysfunction, loss of proteostasis, and neuroinflammation, are likely to exacerbate the vulnerability of DA neurons, underscoring the importance of studying PD within the context of ageing.

Animal models, particularly mice, serve as invaluable tools for studying the molecular and cellular mechanisms underlying PD and ageing. Mice offer several advantages, including genetic manipulability, well-characterized brain anatomy, and the availability of established PD models, the latter including those involving α -synuclein aggregation, deletion or mutation of PD-related genes, or toxin-induced DA neuronal loss (Rocha et al., 2023). These models enable the study of PD pathology and the role of ageing in a controlled and reproducible manner. A critical feature of the characterization of mouse PD models is the quantification of the integrity of the DA system. This is typically performed by quantifying the number of DA neurons in the ventral midbrain and in particular in the SNpc. This is often accompanied by a quantification of the density of the DA neuron axonal markers in the dorsal striatum whose main projections arise from SNpc DA neurons.

This protocol outlines detailed procedures for the collection, processing, and analysis of mouse brain tissue to quantify the number of DA neurons in the SNpc. It includes standardised methods for brain harvesting, fixation, sectioning, immunohistochemical staining for tyrosine hydroxylase (TH) and unbiased stereological quantification of neuronal cell body number. Members of the PD-AGE consortium (a network of experts focused on ageing and PD research; <https://sheffield.ac.uk/pd-age/about>) recognised that significant variability exists in the methodologies for brain sectioning, immunohistochemical staining for TH, and stereological analysis of DA neurons. This variability likely contributes to an increase in variance in experimental results across studies, complicating efforts to compare and integrate data and to draw meaningful conclusions. A standardised protocol is therefore essential to ensure reproducibility and reliability to facilitate cross-study comparisons and advance the field.

The protocol detailed here emphasizes critical steps to preserve tissue integrity, maintain anatomical accuracy, and achieve reliable quantitative results. By following these procedures, researchers can generate robust data to support cross-study comparisons and advance our understanding of the relationship between ageing and PD.

Development of the protocol

Protocols from each participating laboratory were collected. Each step was compared to identify commonalities and differences. A meeting was held to reconcile the differences and discuss the value of alternative options for some steps. A final version of the protocol was agreed upon, which is described below.

Materials

Animals

- These procedures were primarily developed using adult C57/BL6/J mice of both sexes.

Reagents

- For anaesthesia, carbon dioxide gas or sodium pentobarbital (Cat#00241326, CDMV) or isoflurane (Cat#19476, CDMV) or 2,2,2-tribromoethanol and tert-amyl alcohol (Avertin)
- Phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) buffer
- 4% paraformaldehyde (PFA) (Cat#441244, Sigma-Aldrich), in PBS or deionised water (dH₂O)
- Sodium phosphate monobasic (Cat#SPM306, BioShop)
- Sodium phosphate dibasic anhydrous (Cat#SPD307, BioShop)
- Sodium acetate (Cat#SAA304, Bioshop)
- Glucose oxidase (Cat#G7141, Sigma-Aldrich)
- 3,3'-Diaminobenzidine (DAB) (Cat#D5905, Sigma-Aldrich)
- Nickel ammonium sulfate (Cat#A1827, Sigma-Aldrich)
- D-glucose (Cat#G8270, Sigma-Aldrich)
- Ammonium chloride (Cat#A9434, Sigma Aldrich)
- Acetic acid (Cat#AC124040010, Fisher Scientific)
- H₂O₂ (Cat#216763, Sigma-Aldrich)
- 0.3% Triton X-100 (Cat#X100, Sigma-Aldrich)
- Dry ice
- Sucrose (Cat#SUC600, BioShop)
- pH meter
- Filters (0.22 µm)
- Ethylene glycol (Cat#ETH001, BioShop)
- Liquid nitrogen, 2-methylbutane (Cat#M32631, Sigma-Aldrich) or dry ice for flash-freezing
- Primary antibody for tyrosine hydroxylase (TH): rabbit anti-TH, Millipore Cat#AB152 (rabbit anti TH, Novus Biologicals Cat#N300109 and chicken anti-TH, Abcam Cat#ab76442 are suitable alternatives and were found to produce very comparable TH immunostaining, as shown below)
- Secondary antibody: Goat anti-rabbit IgG, Vector Labs BA-1000 (Goat anti-rabbit IgG, Jackson ImmunoResearch 111-065-045 is an alternative). Goat anti-chicken IgY, Vector Labs BA-9010 should be used with Abcam Cat#ab76442.
- Streptavidin horseradish peroxidase (Cat#GERPN1231-2ML, Sigma-Aldrich)
- Cresyl violet (Cat#C-5042, Sigma-Aldrich)
- Permout (Cat#SP15-100, Fisher Scientific)
- Xylene (Cat#X5SK4, Fisher Scientific)
- Isopropanol, (Cat#470301-464, Avantor)
- Ethanol 100%.

Supplier information:

- ABCAM, USA, www.abcam.com

- Avantor, Canada, www.avantorsciences.com/ca
- Bioshop, Canada, www.bioshopcanada.com
- CDMV, Canada, www.cdmv.com/
- Fisher Scientific, Canada, www.fishersci.ca
- Jackson ImmunoResearch, USA, www.jacksonimmuno.com
- Novus Biological, Canada, www.novusbio.com
- Sigma-Aldrich, Canada, www.sigmaaldrich.com
- Vector Labs, USA, www.vectorlabs.com

Solutions

- 30% sucrose solution composition (500ml, 10ml per brain is needed):
 1. Measure 2.691 g of sodium phosphate monobasic and 4.331 g of sodium phosphate dibasic anhydrous.
 2. Add these salts to a beaker containing approximately 400 ml of dH₂O.
 3. Stir the mixture until the salts are completely dissolved.
 4. Add 150 g of sucrose to the solution.
 5. Continue stirring until the sucrose is fully dissolved.
 6. Adjust the pH of the solution to 7.4 with NaOH 0.1N using a pH meter.
 7. Add additional dH₂O to bring the total volume up to 500 ml.
 8. Filter the solution through a 0.2 µm filter to ensure sterility.
 9. Store the solution at 4°C until use.
- Cryoprotectant solution composition 6 ml per brain):
 1. Prepare 30% sucrose solution as mentioned above.
 2. Add ethylene glycol to 30% of the composition of the solution.
 3. Filter the solution through a 0.2 µm filter to ensure sterility.
 4. Store the solution at 4°C until use.
- 0.2 M acetate buffer pH 6.0
 - Prepare 1 L of 0.2 M sodium acetate.
 - Prepare 1 L of 0.2 N acetic acid.
 - Mix 900 ml of 0.2 M sodium acetate and 51.7 ml of 0.2 N acetic acid
 - Top up to 1 L with dH₂O.
 - Check the pH (should be 6.0).
- Glucose oxidase solution (1mg/ml)
 - Mix 2 mg of glucose oxidase with 2 ml of 0.05M acetate buffer.
- DAB (3,3'-Diaminobenzidine) solution
 - Mix 10 mg of DAB with 1 ml dH₂O.
 - Vortex for 1 min to completely dissolve the DAB.
- DAB reaction mixture
 - In 5 ml of 0.2 M acetate Buffer pH 6.0, add 250 mg of nickel ammonium sulfate, 20 mg of D-glucose, and 4 mg of ammonium chloride.
 - Once the nickel ammonium sulfate is dissolved, add 5 ml dH₂O.
 - Add 80 ul of glucose oxidase solution.
 - Filter with a 0.22 µm syringe filter.
- 0.1M acetate buffer
 - Mix 500 ml of 0.2 M acetate buffer and 500 ml of dH₂O.
 - For 0.05 M acetate buffer, mix 100 ml of 0.1 M acetate buffer and 100 ml of dH₂O.
- 0.9% H₂O₂
 - Add 90 µl of a solution of 30% H₂O₂, top to 10 ml with PBS.
- PBS containing 0.3% Triton X-100
 - Add 3 ul of Triton X-100 per 1ml of PBS.

Equipment

- Anaesthesia set up: IP injection set up or an induction chamber
- Peristaltic pump or manual syringe system for trans-cardiac perfusion
- Dissection tools such as scalpels, forceps, scissors and razor blades.
- Cryostat or microtome
- Glass staining dishes with 8-section staining nets
- Charged glass slides
- Coverslips
- MicroBrightField Stereo Investigator software for stereological counting
- Widefield microscope with motorized stage and camera with 10x air and 100x oil immersion lens, compatible with Stereo Investigator software.

Procedure

Brain Harvesting

1.1 Anaesthesia

Administer anaesthesia according to the legal requirements of the country where the project is being conducted. It is not believed that the different methods of anaesthesia are a major source of variability. Options include:

- CO₂
- Sodium pentobarbital (100 mg/kg, 7 mg/ml, IP)
- Isoflurane, followed by cervical dislocation for secondary confirmation of death
- Tribromoethanol (Avertin) (125-300 mg/kg, IP)

1.2 Perfusion

Perform trans-cardiac perfusion using 50 ml of phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) followed by 50 ml of 4% PFA to fix the entire brain.

CRITICAL STEP: post-mortem delay: The time between perfusion and brain harvest significantly impacts tissue quality. Aim to collect brains within 1-2 min after death for optimal results.

Note: Perfusion with PFA is required to maintain anatomical details critical for precise cell counting. Investigators sometimes prefer to use half of the brain for biochemical analyses and the other half for striatal TH immunostaining or biochemical analyses. In this case, mice can be perfused with saline to remove blood before extracting the brain and preserving one-half of the brain in PFA for histological analysis. However, for stereological quantification of the number of SNpc and ventral tegmental area (VTA) DA neurons, structures that are close to the midline, it is preferable to not cut the brain in half and instead use complete brains. Rapid processing of the brain immediately after extraction is essential to minimise variability. Delays in PFA fixation can compromise anatomical integrity and increase variability.

1.3 Brain Extraction

Immediately remove the brain after perfusion.

1.4 Post-Fixation

Post-fix the brain for 12-48h at 4°C in 10ml 4% PFA. Add gauze to the tube to push the brain down and make sure it is fully submerged. While 12h is sufficient for smaller brain samples, 48h should be used for complete brains.

1.5 Tissue Processing

Transfer the brain to a 30% sucrose solution in a 15 ml tube at 4°C and wait until it sinks to the bottom of the tube (approximately 48-96h).

1.6 Freezing

Flash-freeze the brain and store at -80°C.

Note: Freezing can be performed by placing the brain on aluminium foil on dry ice (-80°C) or by submerging the brain into liquid 2-methylbutane at -30°C until it stops bubbling.

1.7 Sectioning

- Use a cryostat, or microtome with dry ice, for sectioning.
- Use a razor blade to cut the brain at its base at the level of the brain stem, creating a flat surface perpendicular to the rostral/caudal axis. Position the brain with olfactory bulbs pointing upwards.
- Adjust the instrument platform so that the rostral/caudal axis is perpendicular to the blade and the dorsal/ventral axis is level with the blade.
- Cut and collect coronal sections from bregma -2.53 mm to -3.88 mm (verify bregma using an atlas).
- Cut sections at a thickness of 40 µm.

1.8 Collection

Collect sections in a 24-well plate prefilled with cryoprotectant solution. Distribute one in every four or six slices in 4 or 6 serial wells.

1.9 Storage

Seal the plate and store it at 4°C. Stain within 2 months.

Note: If staining cannot be done within 2 months, keep the tissue in antifreeze solution at -20°C.

Brain Tissue Staining

2.1 Primary antibody

- Tyrosine hydroxylase (TH)
 - Catalogue Number: Millipore Cat# AB152, Rabbit anti-TH

- Dilution: 1:1000

Other primary antibodies often used include Novus Biologicals N300109 (rabbit anti-TH, dilution, 1:1000) and Abcam ab76442 (chicken anti-TH, dilution 1:1000). As shown below, the three antibodies are comparable, although the two rabbit antibodies produce stronger signal at the commonly used concentrations.

2.2 Secondary Antibody

- Goat anti-Rabbit Biotin
 - Catalogue Number: Vector Labs BA-1000
 - Dilution: 1:500

Note: Another acceptable secondary antibody is Jackson ImmunoResearch 111-065-045 (1:100). If a chicken primary antibody is used (ab76442), the goat anti-chicken Vector Labs BA-9010 (1:500) should be used instead.

2.3 Staining Procedure

This protocol was optimized using the TH antibody Cat# AB152 from Millipore.

1. Perform staining in glass dishes using 8-section staining nets.
2. Wash with 0.01M PBS (3x for 10 min each). Use cell strainers for all washing steps.
3. Block endogenous peroxidase activity by washing in 0.01M PBS containing 0.9% H₂O₂ (1x for 10 min).
4. Wash again in PBS (3x for 10 min each).
5. Incubate the sections with the primary antibody in PBS containing 0.3% Triton X-100 for 48h at 4°C with stirring.
6. Wash in PBS (3x for 10 minutes each).
7. Incubate with the secondary antibody in PBS containing 0.3% Triton X-100 for 12h at 4°C with stirring.
8. Wash in 0.01M PBS (3x for 10 min each).
9. Incubate in streptavidin horseradish peroxidase (1:200) for 3h at room temperature with stirring in PBS containing 0.3% Triton X-100.
10. Wash in PBS (3x for 10 min each).
11. Prepare the DAB reaction mixture, add the slices and allow the reaction to proceed for 0.5-10 min under stirring (45s for TH staining).
12. Stop the reaction by washing the sections in 0.1M acetate buffer (1x for 10 min).
13. Mount sections on charged slides in 0.1M acetate buffer and allow slides to dry for 48-96h (96h preferred to avoid sections detaching).
14. Perform additional cresyl violet staining and dehydration steps as described, followed by clearing in xylene and coverslipping with Permount.
 - 2 min dH₂O
 - 2 min cresyl violet (30 min at 37°C before staining)
 - 1 min dH₂O
 - 1 min dH₂O
 - 1 min EtOH 50%
 - 1 min EtOH 70%

- 1 min EtOH 90%
- 10 dips in EtOH 90%
- 1 min EtOH 100%
- 1 min Isopropanol
- 2 min Xylene

2.4 Comparison of three suggested anti-TH primary antibodies

Considering that three different anti tyrosine hydroxylase (TH) antibodies have been used by different laboratories linked to the PD-AGE consortium, we compared them head-to-head on mesencephalic and striatal brain sections prepared using a cryostat. We compared the Millipore AB152, rabbit anti-TH (dilution: 1:1000), the Novus Biologicals N300109 rabbit anti-TH (dilution: 1:1000) and the Abcam ab76442 chicken anti-TH (dilution 1:1000) at their most commonly used concentrations. **Figure 1** shows representative images of the ventral midbrain of wild-type C57/BL6/J mice including the SNpc obtained with the three antibodies detected with secondary antibodies coupled to horseradish peroxidase. As can be seen, the three antibodies each used at their optimal concentration labelled DA neurons with very similar signal to noise ratio.

Figure 1: Immunohistochemical labelling of mouse ventral midbrain sections using three anti-TH primary antibodies. DA neurons and their dendritic processes can be identified by the black stain. The images on the right show a higher power magnification of some of the cell bodies located in the SNpc.

The same three primary anti-TH antibodies were also used to label coronal striatal sections obtained from C57/BL6/J mice injected unilaterally in the dorsal striatum with 2µL of a 5 mg/mL

solution of 6-OHDA to induce a partial lesion to the DA system (**Fig. 2A**, lesion on the left side). The protocol used for the stereotaxic 6-OHDA lesion and for the striatal section immunohistochemistry is not described in detail here, but can be found in a previous publication (Giguère et al., 2019) and in a published protocol (<https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.rm7vzj6rrlx1/v1>). Images were acquired using a 40X objective and a Zeiss Axioscan slide scanner. **Figures 2B and 2C** show that the two rabbit TH primary antibodies gave very comparable results, while **figure 2D** shows that the chicken TH antibody produced a signal of lower intensity under the conditions used. However, the signal obtained was still adequate to visualise TH positive axonal varicosities when the display was adjusted by changing the look-up table. Due to this lower signal, the chicken antibody was not as efficient to report the extent of the striatal TH loss due to the 6-OHDA lesion (**Fig. 2F**). However, a quantification of the signal to noise ratio estimated by comparing the intensity of TH immunoreactivity in the striosome and matrix compartments of striatal sections revealed that the three antibodies provided similar signal to noise ratios (**Fig. 2G**). These results confirm that although each of the three antibodies used can be appropriate to detect and quantify the number of DA neurons in stereological counting experiments, the two rabbit TH antibodies appear to be better suited to quantify striatal TH innervation density in mouse PD models. Further adjustments such as using higher concentrations of the AB76442 chicken antibody or other goat anti-chicken secondary antibodies could perhaps compensate for the reduced signal obtained with this antibody.

Figure 2: Evaluation of three anti-TH primary antibodies for immunohistochemical labelling of striatal sections from 6-OHDA unilaterally lesioned mice. (**A**) Representative images of TH-

immunoreactivity in orange and DAPI signal in blue on the lesioned (left) and contralateral (right) hemispheres obtained with the AB152 anti-TH antibody. The axonal varicosities of DA neurons can be identified in these images by the orange signal. **(B-E)** Representative, higher magnification images of a region in the dorsal striatum showing the signal obtained with the AB152 **(B)**, NB300109 **(C)** and AB76442 **(D-E)** antibodies. The image in panel E shows the same signal as panel D, but with the look-up table adjusted to better reveal the signal obtained with the AB76442 TH antibody. The axonal varicosities of DA neurons can be identified in these images by the orange signal. Secondary antibodies used were the goat-anti-rabbit Alexa Fluor 546 (A-11010, Thermofisher Scientific, 1:500) and the goat-anti-chicken (CF543, Biotium, 20311, 1:500). **(F)** Quantification of the intensity of TH immunoreactivity in the 6-OHDA-lesioned and non-lesioned (contralateral) sides of the striatum. **(G)** Quantification of the signal to noise ratio of the three anti-TH antibodies, estimated by quantifying the intensity of the TH signal in the striosome and matrix compartments of the striatum.

Stereological analysis

3.1 Stereological counting

1. Use the Stereo Investigator stereology software program (from MBF Bioscience) and an optical fractionator probe (a feature available within the software for accurate 3D counting).
2. Enter parameters on the software: section interval of 4 and section thickness cut at 40 μm , as recommended.
3. Trace the SNpc and VTA DA neuron regions of interest at low magnification (e.g. 10x) **(Figure 3)**.

Note: Counting DA neurons in the VTA is not necessary, but useful to determine if any observed loss of DA neurons is selective for the SNpc.

Note: Use a standard adult mouse brain atlas for guidance. Counterstains like crystal violet or cresyl violet highlight nuclei and facilitate the visualisation of cell morphology.

Figure 3 legend: Identification of the substantia nigra pars compacta (SNpc) and the ventral tegmental area (VTA) in a mouse ventral midbrain section. **(A)** Low magnification image of a coronal mouse brain section stained for tyrosine hydroxylase (TH) with a cresyl violet counterstain. **(B)** Higher magnification image of the same structures. The SNpc is in red and the VTA in green.

4. Switch to a high magnification oil objective (e.g., 100x) for cell counting.
5. We recommend that the size of the counting frame be 60x60 μm or large enough to count 1 to 3 neurons per frame on average and that the grid size is 150x150 μm . Ensuring that the counting frame is not so large helps to prevent "edge effects" and thus improves the reliability of the counts.
6. Set the sampling interval to every fourth section.
7. Measure the mounted section thickness at every 6 sites to account for shrinkage.
8. The top and bottom 2 μm of each section are excluded from counting due to potential damage inherent to tissue slicing.
9. Counting Rules
 - Dopaminergic (TH+) (brown staining) and non-dopaminergic cells (violet staining) are both counted. With the cresyl violet staining, it is possible to distinguish and count separately non-dopaminergic neurons (TH-) and glial cells, distinguishable by the larger size of neuronal cell bodies. Non-TH neuron counts help assess whether neuronal loss is global or specific to DA neurons. Glial cell count helps assess potential inflammation.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Neurons are fully inside the counting frame.
- Neurons touching the GREEN lines.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Neurons are completely outside the counting frame.
- Neurons touching RED lines.
- Neurons touching both GREEN and RED lines simultaneously.
- Neurons outside the traced ROI are not counted.

An example of the application of these inclusion and exclusion criteria is provided in **Figure 4**.

Figure 4 legend: Stereological counting of dopaminergic neurons in the substantia nigra pars compacta (SNpc) using Stereo Investigator software. **(A)** Schematic outline of the SNpc with one counting frame. **(B)** Schematic representation of the counting frame (red and green square) with the boundary of the region of interest (ROI) in dashed lines. Cells falling within the counting frame and inside the ROI are counted (YES). Cells falling outside of the ROI or outside of the counting frame are not counted (NO). **(C)** Representative image of a tyrosine hydroxylase (TH) stained section visualized at 100X magnification with TH positive (star) and TH negative (triangle) neurons falling inside (green) or outside (red) of the counting frame.

10. The formula for estimated cell counts is presented below:

The total estimated cell count (**N**) is calculated using the formula:

$$N = \Sigma[Q \times (1/SSF) \times (1/ASF) \times (1/TSF)]$$

where,

N = Number of estimated cells.

Q = Number of counted markers.

SSF = Section sampling fraction.

ASF = Area sampling fraction.

TSF = Thickness sampling fraction.

11. Use the Gundersen coefficient to assess the precision of the count. Aim for a coefficient of less than 0.1.

Note: If cell loss is extreme (e.g., 90%), achieving a good coefficient is challenging due to low cell counts. For moderate cell loss (e.g., 20-50%), maintaining consistent parameters is more feasible. Using a smaller interval for more frames can result in better condition coefficients.

Note: To account for variability while counting

1. It is preferable to always have the same, well-trained individuals perform the neuronal countings within a project. When training a new individual, it is recommended to have them first count previously counted (standard) brains and to have them repeatedly count the same sections multiple times until their counts stabilise.
2. Always assess the variability of counting by a single counter for each experiment. To do so, make sure each counter recounts a proportion of their already counted slides in a blinded manner - the recounted number should be less than 10% compared to the initial count.
3. If it is required to have more than one person involved in the neuronal countings, it is recommended to have the second counter re-count a subset of animals to ensure a maximum of 10% variability between counters.
4. To optimize inter-rater reliability, it is also good practice to have the second person recount the number of neurons in the SNpc and VTA based on the tracing of these structures performed by the first person, and vice versa.

References

Giguère N, Delignat-Lavaud B, Herborg F, Voisin A, Li Y, Jacquemet V, Anand-Srivastava M, Gether U, Giros B, Trudeau L-É (2019) Increased vulnerability of nigral dopamine neurons after expansion of their axonal arborization size through D2 dopamine receptor conditional knockout. *PLoS Genet* 15:e1008352.

Rocha E et al. (2023) Aging, Parkinson's Disease, and Models: What Are the Challenges? *Aging Biol* 1:e20230010.

Acknowledgements

We are grateful to Dr. Ilaria Bellantuono for her support in coordinating the standardisation of this protocol and to Dr. Elezabeth Stephen for her help in putting together this manuscript and managing the PD-AGE initiative.